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Abstract:

Every aspect of human life has some or the other fixed value and it is important in every sphere of life. Man is engaged in understanding, continuous preservation, nourishment and presentation of the values of different spheres of his life. His various desires are also fulfilled through these. In this study, we will discuss religious values and moral values-

Religious Values:

The etymological meaning of religion is - one who sustains, one who nourishes. In Indian tradition, religion has a deep relation with man, his life and culture. Human life gets balance by relying on religion. The understanding of these values strengthens co-existence, universal brotherhood and social rules and regulations in human life.

India has a very glorious past. Indian culture and knowledge tradition is the most ancient and rich tradition of the world which is focused on spiritualism and the feeling of soul rather than worldliness and materialism. While various cultures of the world established materialistic values in their way of life, Indian culture imbibed religion and spirituality in its way of life. In Indian culture, the feeling of considering the whole world as one's own family is inherent with the objectives of 'Sarvajan Hitaye, Sarvajan Sukhaye' and 'Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam'. Along with this, the main goal is to establish life values like peace, tolerance, unity, truth, non-violence and good conduct and to bring about spiritual progress in the whole world.

The basic foundation of Indian knowledge tradition is Vedas. Apart from Vedic texts, spiritual and religious values have been discussed like other values in Upanishads, Valmiki Ramayana, Mahabharata, Puranas, Buddhist and Jain texts as well as various genres of Hindi literature (drama, novel, poem, story etc.). Life values are at their peak in Tulsidas's 'Ramcharitmanas'. Its hero Ram is a symbol of life values and ideals. Religious values have been protected by him. At present, from the point of view of religious and other values, the ideals of Ramcharitmanas and Maryada Purushottam Ram are highly relevant and exemplary.

In the ancient educational tradition of India, the Guru used to preach his disciple to follow Dharma at the time of his farewell after the completion of his education. In a way, Dharma has importance in various fields. Satyavrat Shastri says- "In India, sages, thinkers, philosophers, writers and critics, all have given Dharma the highest place and have praised it immensely. If Dharma is protected, it protects, if Dharma is destroyed, it destroys- 'Dharma eva hato hanti dharmo rakshati rakshitah.'"¹ From a philosophical point of view, there is an unbreakable bond between Dharma and ethics. In this regard, Dr. Harish Sethi says- "Dharma is the name of individual and collective ethics. Dharma does not support any such act which is not ethical. The real form of Dharma is not related to rituals and superstitions. Under the shelter of Dharma, co-existence, universal brotherhood and social rules and regulations get strengthened in human life. In this way, religion brings balance to human life."² In fact, religion and its related values have a special significance in human life and social context.

Among religious values, salvation is considered to be the ultimate value because it helps a human to attain his pure form. Scholars have described various characteristics of religion in their scriptures. Eight characteristics of religion have been described in Hitopadesha-

"Sacrifice, study, charity, austerity, truth, patience, forgiveness.

This path of righteousness, called non-greed, is said to be of eight kinds."³

That is, sacrifice, study (study of scriptures), charity, penance, truth, patience, forgiveness and non-greed are the eight paths of religion. According to Emperor Ashoka, "Daya daane sache sochaye madave, sadhave" i.e. compassion, charity, truth, cleanliness, benevolence and saintliness are religion."⁴ At its core lies the feeling of inspiration for human action. Dr. Dharmपाल Maini has included faith in the unmanifested power, devotion to God, kirtan, singing praises, prayer etc. under religious values. In this way, worshipping the saguna or nirguna form of the divine power through various means is a religious value. With the help of these values, man establishes ideals and directs his mind from selfishness to altruism.

In tradition, religion was not seen as separate from life. Man and society have had faith and belief in religion directly or indirectly. It was through religion that the opposing tendencies and deadlocks of the primitive human society were controlled. In ancient society, when the state and laws did not exist, people

followed social rules inspired by religious sentiments. In Indian history, many big wars and revolutions took place for the observance and protection of religion. At that time, religion was the medium of patriotism under which many religious leaders like Mahavira, Buddha, Muhammad, Jesus brought many changes in the world based on religious values.

It is clear that religion has a special significance in Indian culture. Religion, the foundation of social and cultural activities, has never been separate from human life. Directly or indirectly, faith in religion has been a specialty in people and society. Since ancient times, religion has acted as a deciding power regarding what is right and wrong in human thinking, contemplation, behavior and action. Motivating humans to act has been the main objective of religion. The significance of human knowledge also lies in doing the right thing. Religion is when humans move towards the field of action with devotion and faith, supporting truth, goodness, justice and morality.

Today, due to modernity, religious values are rapidly disintegrating and changing. In this context, Dr. Sethi says, "The medieval cultural outlook was religion-based, religious sentiments and values had prominence in society. All worldly conduct was based on religion. Unwavering faith can be seen in the context of salvation, karmavada and reincarnation. Due to this so-called effect of modernity, man was freed from his faith in God, and development in the form of scientific advancement and inventions brought about a radical change in the traditional religious values and unwavering faith in the power of God."⁵ It is true that in today's materialistic age, religious values are declining. Along with the change in the traditional form of religion, its different forms are being found.

The traditional form of religion is changing according to the times. The way the scientific age has exposed religious superstitions, dogmas and ostentation, the feeling of disbelief towards traditional religion is becoming stronger among the youth. In the modern generation, disbelief and distrust towards religion and God is increasing. Now the traditional, emotional form of religious values is being interpreted intellectually, which is an indication of the changing values towards traditional religion.

Today, the definitions and forms of religious values may have changed depending on the situation and time. Religion is being attacked by modern technological development, but still religion is alive because the ultimate goal of different forms of religion is human religion. In this context, Dr. Harish Sethi has said- "There may be different forms of religion, but the final merger of all is human religion. The traditional form of religion related to emotionality is now being interpreted by testing it on the touchstone of intellectualism. But it is certain that it is necessary to have a scientific approach towards religion and religious values. Science is based on facts and searches for truth. Religion also searches for truth. Religion acts as a deciding power of right and wrong in the thinking, contemplation, behavior and action of human beings. In fact, religion is a great support for human beings."⁶

Clearly, in the present context, transformation in religious values is natural. However, a substantial change in the traditional perception of religion is actually a state of valuelessness because while the traditional values have been disintegrated, the new values have not been fully established.

Therefore, we have to remain loyal to these values because religion has been the main source of various values in the world. Faith in life values increases only through religion. Human beings can establish ideals with the help of religious values and direct their mind from selfishness to altruism.

Moral Values:

It is true that the best culmination of moral values is found in religion only. While 'Niti' is an action and method of taking life to the goal, it is also a kind of ideology by which man strengthens his social structure. According to the Hindi dictionary, "Niti means good conduct, best behavior, good trick or a measure based on political wisdom."⁷ The corrupt form of Niti is Naitik. Truth, honesty, love, good conduct, kindness, friendship etc. are called moral values.

The feeling arising from morality is called morality. Morality is a unique quality of man because only a respectable creature can understand and experience morality. It is on the strength of morality that man, with his self-consciousness, discretion and intelligence, can judge good-bad, truth-falsehood, justice-injustice, whereas non-human beings completely lack moral consciousness. Man gives meaning to moral values and morality only with his discretion. According to Dr. Sukhdev Shukla, "Morality means that specific rule-system or code of conduct that directs the conduct of a person, which the society creates for its members."⁸ Morality only speeds up the development process of human life and refines its conduct and behavior. Human behavior is deeply related to morality. In this regard, Dr. Mangatram Bhatia says- "A person can prevent his values from being revealed, but behavior cannot be saved from the eyes of others for a long time. Therefore, values are related to the basis of internal thinking, whereas morality is related to practical conduct."⁹ Morality results from this conduct and devotion to duty of man.

Morality is the fundamental basis of society, which determines what is right and wrong and gives an ideal form to the society. If we look at the moral criteria, then the meaning and accuracy of values are evaluated in the social context only. But due to the different forms of morality found in different sections of the society, there is conflict and dispute on the question of moral and immoral. In this situation, morality is tested on the criterion of 'Bahujan Hitaay Bahujan Sukhaay'. Generally, the work done from the point of view of human interest is moral. For example - 'killing of a living being' is called a sin, which is also in accordance with the policy. At the same time, the work done from the point of view of wider human interest, such as - killing of enemies or massacre to protect the national interest, is also moral from the point of view of 'Bahujan Hitaay Bahujan Sukhaay'. Thus, it can be said that morality is that social thing

and ideal, which gives a peaceful and civilized form to the society. In this regard it has been said - "If values are the goal, then morality is the way to achieve them. The combined form of these two culminates in 'moral values'. It is the observance of morality and human values that elevates man from the status of an animal to the level of humanity."¹⁰

Moral values have their own separate existence. However, moral values cannot be seen separately from social values because they are complementary to each other. Moral values are bound by moral customs and ideals. Morality increases the social prestige of a person. The understanding of these values leads to the welfare of man, society, nation and the world. Therefore, moral values are related to the entire life. Regarding the source of moral values, Dr. Dharamvir Bharti says that "In the period of the rise of humanism, the tendency of considering man as the creator of these values instead of considering any supremacy like God or his representative religious leaders as the dictator of moral values had started developing."¹¹

Today scientific thinking has given a new direction to morality. A lot has changed in the change of philosophy of life. In this era of change, the decline of traditional moral values has increased. New morality was born as a result of the difference in various viewpoints. The values that were traditionally considered inappropriate in various fields of life are now being accepted as appropriate. Today's changing circumstances are the main reason for the disintegration of moral values. This is why there is a conflict between new moral concepts and traditional values. At present, the new contact of modernization and transportation has brought about a confluence of different cultures of the country. By looking at the cultural and moral values of our country in the context of the cultures of other nations, it becomes clear that in the attraction of novelty, we are rapidly adopting western moral values as a 'fashion' today. The traditional beliefs of religion and morality are also being disintegrated by the ideologies of Marx and Freud.

In fact, in ancient society, religion and morality were largely the same. But with the changing circumstances of development, the difference between the two has become visible. Even though morality has sometimes been declared irreligious along with traditional religious deeds, modern man cannot be opposed to religion and morality. Human religion follows morality. Moral values are based on intellect rather than sentimentality. It insists on the prestige of truth. In this, human religion is closer to the person than traditional religion. Earlier, sin and virtue were analyzed on the basis of religion, but in the changing circumstances of the present time, sin and virtue have started being considered from the point of view of morality along with religion. Human perspective has started getting importance in the consideration of 'good' and 'bad', 'right' and 'wrong', 'sin' and 'virtue'. Traditional religious beliefs based on superstitions have been broken.

It is clear that morality always points towards good. Man may do immoral acts for personal reasons or benefits, but it is only from the moral point of view that it is judged correctly. It is also true that like values, the form of morality also keeps changing according to the country and time. The basic reasons for this change are new social consciousness, faith, belief, human dignity etc. In fact, moral values play an important role in giving an ideal form to the society. In the absence of morality and ethical values, a situation of anarchy arises in the society.

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